

Globalization, Fiscal Decentralization, and Environmental Degradation in OECD Countries

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ABSTRACT: This study highlights the impact of globalization and fiscal decentralization on environmental degradation in OECD countries using panel data from 1995 to 2020. For data analysis, panel ADF test and panel ARDL model are applied. The study found that globalization is negatively and significantly related to the environmental deterioration in OECD countries. Similarly, expenditure decentralization is found to be a contributing factor to environmental degradation. In contrast, revenue decentralization is negatively and significantly related to environmental degradation. The variables population and energy use are also positive, while inflation rate is negatively related to the environmental degradation. The findings suggested that OECD countries must implement policies that curtail the adverse effects of globalization and fiscal decentralization on the environment.

Keywords: Globalization, Fiscal Decentralization, Environmental Degradation, OECD Countries

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1. Introduction

Globalization is the collective term for a collection of economic, social, and political structures and processes that arise from intra or intercontinental networks of people, the ties between which are mediated by national economies, cultures, technology, and governance. Globalization promotes national economic, social, and political development, which in turn boosts economic growth. On the other hand, Globalization also increases CO₂ emissions, which cause environmental degradation and climate change. Globalization has three effects on the environment, such as the composition effect, the income effect, and the technique effect. According to the income effect, increased trade and foreign investment cause globalization to increase CO₂ emissions. The technique effect of globalization helps nations produce environmentally friendly goods by bringing in energy-efficient technologies, which lowers CO₂ emissions. However, the development of information and communication

technology (ICT) does not lower energy consumption during operations. As a result, the more ICT is developed, the more energy is consumed, which may lead to increased CO₂ emissions into the atmosphere. Globalization produces different forms of production in the composition effect. As a result, businesses are encouraged to relocate their production and operations to developing nations where environmental laws are less stringent, owing to the severe environmental regulations found in industrialized nations. Relocation results in the pollution haven effect, which causes polluting firms to relocate from developed to developing nations.

On the other hand, government spending on environmental protection is expected to be naturally influenced by fiscal decentralization, which also greatly impacts environmental innovation (Zhou et al., 2020). Fiscal decentralization consists of a framework for giving a lower level of government authority over revenue, spending, and the related liabilities (Xiao-Sheng et al., 2022; Du & Sun, 2021). Fiscal decentralization significantly lowers the expenses of pollution treatment and pollutant discharge fees. In other words, the decentralization of national financing can enhance local environmental governance and optimize the influence of industrial policies on implementation (He, 2015).

Problem Statement

When examining the relationship between fiscal decentralization and environmental sustainability, the literature currently supports two concepts: the race to the top concept, which holds that giving authority and funding to local governments at the sub-level effectively reduces the negative externalities brought on by human activities (Khan et al., 2021; Safi et al., 2022). The use of stringent environmental regulations to limit negative externalities resulting from human activities justifies the race to the top strategy, which links fiscal decentralization to environmental sustainability (Khan et al., 2021). In contrast, the race to the bottom strategy involves governments easing domestic environment rules to entice international businesses to participate in their economies. In this case, the entry of foreign businesses and industries leads to environmental damage without strict environmental regulations (Khan et al., 2023).

Keeping in view the above discussion, growing concerns exist about the relationship between globalization, fiscal decentralization and the environmental degradation. To achieve sustainable growth, decision-makers must comprehend this long-term link. Environmental, social, and economic concerns need to be considered to achieve such development (Wu et al., 2022). Some scholars have demonstrated how fiscal decentralization affects government spending on environmental protection, they have not directly investigated the impact of revenue fiscal decentralization and expenditures fiscal decentralization on environmental degradation in OECD. It is yet unclear how revenue fiscal decentralization will affect pollution control dynamically. The study also analyzes the effects of political, social and economic globalization on environmental degradation. Therefore, this study is novel to analyze the influence of fiscal decentralization and globalization on environmental degradation in OECD countries. The study outcomes will provide important

implications to design policies about environmental protection by considering the role of globalization and fiscal decentralization.

2. Literature Review

Different studies explored the influence of globalization and fiscal decentralization on environmental degradation. In this section, the literature review of recently conducted studies has been presented.

Studies of the Impact of Globalization on Environmental Degradation

Globalization promotes national economic, social, and political development, which in turn boosts economic growth (Dreher, 2006; Gygli et al., 2019). Different scholars analyzed the impact of globalization on environmental degradation such as Awad & Mallek (2023) analyzed the data of 44 Sub-Saharan African countries between 2003 and 2020 to examine the relationship between economic globalization and environmental quality. Results showed that information and communications technology and globalization have a direct negative impact on the environmental degradation. Furthermore, the outcomes demonstrated that the negative environmental effects of globalization might be mitigated by information and communication technology services. Wu et al., (2022) analyzed the relationship between globalization and the environment in China, US and India using data from 1970 to 2018. The findings showed that the long-term relationship between globalization and the environment is integrated in the United States. The environmental in India and the United States was getting better in the short-run due to globalization. However, globalization, meanwhile, was causing environmental damage in China. Using data from 1971 to 2018, Akadiri et al., (2022) investigated the effects of real income, urbanization, globalization, and energy use on environmental deterioration in Nigeria. The findings demonstrated that energy consumption, urbanization, real income, and globalization contributing to environmental degradation. Using data from 1974 to 2017, Rehman et al., (2021) investigated the effects of trade, energy consumption, globalization, and economic growth on Pakistan's ecological footprint. The results demonstrated that trade openness, GDP growth, globalization, and energy consumption have positive interactions with the ecological footprint. The causal relationship between the globalization index and CO2 emissions from 1980 to 2017 was carried out by Umar et al., (2020). They discovered that improved environmental outcomes were a direct result of globalization. Using panel data from NAFTA nations, Kalayci & Hayaloglu (2019) investigated the connection between globalization and CO2 emissions. According to their findings, trade openness and economic globalization have a detrimental effect on CO2 emissions. Similarly, Shahbaz et al., (2018) examined how globalization affected Japan's CO2 emissions using annual data from 1970 to 2014, considering factors like energy consumption and economic growth that may impact carbon emissions. An asymmetric threshold version of the ARDL model is used to address the structural breaks and asymmetries resulting from policy adjustments. The study showed that globalization causes threshold-based positive and negative shocks that raise carbon emissions. Growth in the economy and energy use both significantly reduced carbon emissions. In the short-run,

energy consumption, economic expansion, and globalization all dramatically raise carbon emissions. Keeping in view the literature review, it is hypothesized that:

H1: Globalization is significantly related to the environmental degradation in OECD countries

Studies of the Impact of Fiscal Decentralization on Environmental Degradation

Globalization also increases CO₂ emissions, which cause environmental degradation and climate change (Mehmood & Tariq, 2020). Different scholars analyzed the impact of fiscal decentralization on environmental degradation using data from South Africa from 1960 to 2020, Udeagha & Breitenbach (2023) investigated the impact of fiscal decentralization on environmental degradation. The results demonstrated the existence of the race to the top hypothesis and demonstrated that fiscal decentralization impacts reducing CO₂ emissions both in the short- and long-run. Economic progress compromised ecological integrity, but it also strengthened ecological protection, supporting the environmental Kuznets curve theory. The results also demonstrated that energy use, trade openness, industrial value-added, and FDI were the main drivers of CO₂ emissions while technological innovation improved ecological integrity. Zhao et al., (2022) investigated the effect of fiscal decentralization on environmental degradation using panel data covering 30 Chinese provinces between 2002 and 2018. The results demonstrated that technological advancement and FDI significantly impede environmental pollution, environmental regulation alone does not play a role in pollution control. Fiscal decentralization also increases the demand for FDI. Using data from Japan from 1994 to 2018, Yuan et al., (2022) examined the impact of fiscal decentralization on CO₂ emissions. The findings showed that fiscal decentralization and renewable energy consumption improve the quality of the atmosphere while GDP trade and non-renewable energy increases the CO₂ emissions in Japan. Khan et al., (2021) examined the impact of fiscal decentralization on CO₂ emissions using a balanced panel dataset of OECD countries from 1990 to 2018. The results indicated that environmental quality was improved by fiscal decentralization. The study also revealed that improvements in institutional quality and human capital development strengthened the relationship between fiscal decentralization and environmental quality. Using a new dynamic panel ARDL model, Phan et al., (2021) investigated the dynamic impact of fiscal decentralization on CO₂ emissions in Asian countries from 1984 to 2017. The findings indicated that the effects of fiscal decentralization on CO₂ emissions were asymmetrical, with a positive shift in income and expenditure decentralization leading to a reduction in CO₂ emissions in Asia. Ji et al., (2021) used data from 1990 to 2018 to examine the impact of fiscal decentralization on CO₂ emissions using data of highly financially decentralized nations. The results demonstrated that fiscal decentralization benefits the environment by lowering CO₂ emissions. Additionally, the GDP rises due to eco-innovation and renewable energy lead to reduce the CO₂ emissions. Keeping in view the literature review, it is hypothesized that:

H1: Fiscal decentralization is significantly related to the environmental degradation in OECD countries

In the literature, it has been observed that different studies examine the impact of fiscal decentralization and globalization on environmental degradation. However, in the context of OECD countries, the literature demonstrates diverse results. The empirical relationship between fiscal decentralization and the environment has been examined in most studies in the literature however, this study utilized fiscal revenue and expenditures decentralization to see its impacts on environmental degradation. Similarly, social, political and political globalization is also considered in this study as a factor to environmental degradation. In terms of policy implication, the study's findings will also be helpful to government officials, environmentalists, and policymakers since they offer a better understanding of environmental sustainability, implications, and supporting evidence. Therefore, the current study is important and will contribute in a literature significantly.

3. Data and Methodology

This study uses panel data from OECD countries from 1995 to 2020. The OECD countries were selected based on data availability. The variables CO2 emissions, population, energy use, and inflation rate data are collected from World Development Indicators (WDI). The revenue fiscal decentralization and expenditure fiscal decentralization data are collected from the Economic Survey of Pakistan, while the globalization data is collected from the KOF globalization index. The following econometric model is developed to analyze the role of globalization and fiscal decentralization in influencing environmental degradation in OECD countries:

$$CO_{2it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SGI_{it} + \beta_2 PGI_{it} + \beta_3 EGI_{it} + \beta_4 FDEC_{it} + \beta_5 FDRC_{it} + \beta_6 EU_{it} + \beta_7 POP_{it} + \beta_8 INF_{it} + u_{it}$$

Where CO2 indicates carbon dioxide emissions as a measure of environmental degradation, SGI indicates the social globalization index, PGI indicates the political globalization index, EDI represents economic globalization index, FDEC represents expenditures fiscal decentralization, FDRC means revenue fiscal decentralization, EU represents energy use, POP indicates total population, INF exhibits inflation rate, and u_{it} indicates error term.

Table 1: Description of Variables

Variables	Decryptions of Variables	
Dependent Variable		
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide emission	Metric tons per capita
Independent Variables		
PGL	Political Globalization	KOF index of globalization
SGL	Social Globalization	KOF index of globalization
EGL	Economic Globalization	KOF index of globalization
FDRC	Revenue Fiscal Decentralization	Fiscal decentralization as measured by sub-national revenue as ratio of total central revenue

FDEC	Expenditures Fiscal Decentralization	Fiscal decentralization as measured by the subnational expenditure as ratio of total central expenditure percentage
POP	Population	Total population
EU	Energy Use	Total energy use
INF	Inflation	Consumer price index

Unit Root Test

In order to verify the stationarity order of the variables, the econometric approach typically recommends testing the unit root property before moving on to the estimating phase. We have utilized the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test to check the stationary level of variables. This analysis provides guidelines for selecting the estimation technique for the long-run parameters. The unit root test operated under the fundamental premise that each unique unit root could be processed across all cross-sections. The lack of a stationarity procedure for the variables is the H_0 for all panel unit root tests.

Panel ARDL Model

Panel ARDL simultaneously estimate the long run and short run inside a single model. Moreover, according to Pesaran et al., (1999), the PMG-ARDL technique is suitable when the series are stationary at level $I(0)$, first difference $I(1)$, and mix of order integration but not at second difference $I(2)$. This model also provides short-run error correction form to analyze the speed of adjustment to move towards long-run equilibrium in case of disturbances. The ARDL model can yield consistent coefficients by approximating each cross-section elasticity's and group averages by the use of the mean group estimator (Pesaran et al., 1999; Pesaran & Smith, 1995). Additionally, they suggested that the hypothesis of homogeneous long-run parameters across cross-sections allows more consistent pooled mean group estimators and short-run elasticity that varies between cross-sections but keeps long-run parameters standardized.

4. Data Analysis

The descriptive statistics of variables is presented in Table 2. It is found that the mean value of CO₂ emissions is 8.335, median value is 8.169, maximum value is 18.520, minimum value is 1.2017, standard deviation is 4.006, skewness value is 0.354, which exhibits the positively skewed distribution, and kurtosis value is 2.964 which indicate platykurtic distribution. Similarly, we can observe the descriptive statistics of other variables from a table.

Table 2: Descriptive Analysis

Variables	Mean	Median	MAX	MIN	S.D.	SK	KURT
CO ₂	8.335	8.169	18.520	1.2017	4.006	0.354	2.964
PGI	69.633	71.765	89.718	40.080	11.464	-0.51	2.582
SGI	76.733	79.941	91.838	41.680	11.235	-1.06	3.454
EGI	70.637	71.607	89.977	29.912	12.769	-0.69	2.918

FDEC	0.483	0.322	9.923	0.0134	0.787	8.132	80.076
FDRC	0.686	0.576	9.212	0.0073	0.965	6.161	43.325
POP	154.041	93.235	531.109	2.343	157.36	0.963	2.655
EU	4163.71	3701.93	18181.15	623.028	2973.2	2.362	11.013
INF	4.366	2.129	143.639	-9.65	9.877	8.2466	92.718

Source: Author's Calculations

We have applied the panel ADF test to check the stationary level of variables. The outcomes are reported in Table 3. The outcomes exhibit that the variables political globalization, economic globalization, population, and inflation rate are stationary at level I(0), while the variables CO2 emissions, social globalization, expenditures fiscal decentralization, revenue fiscal decentralization, and energy use are integrated at first order I(1). Therefore, the mixed order of integration suggests that the panel ARDL model is suitable for the long-run estimation of parameters.

Table 3: Panel Unit Root Test Analysis

Variables	Level		1st Difference		Results
	T-test	P-Value	T-test	P-Value	
CO₂	--	--	3.13	0.000	I(1)
PGL	-3.482	0.071	--	--	I(0)
SGL	--	--	-1.402	0.000	I(1)
EGL	-3.284	0.514	--	--	I(0)
FDEC	--	--	-3.553	0.000	I(1)
FDRC	--	--	-4.041	0.024	I(1)
POP	-3.619	0.720	--	--	I(0)
EU	--	--	-3.586	0.112	I(1)
INF	-2.119	0.318	--	--	I(0)

Source: Author's Calculations

Table 4 reports the outcomes of the panel long-run ARDL model. It is found that social, political and economic globalization is positively and significantly related to the CO2 emissions in OECD countries. The coefficient values of SGI, PGI, and EGI indicate that as these variables increase by one unit, the CO2 emissions lead to an increase of 0.2761, 0.6561, and 0.3266 units, respectively. It suggests that globalization has significant negative effects on the environment across economies, it also promotes economic growth through trade and financial openness (Shahbaz et al., 2015). More energy is needed for economic expansion, increased industrialization, and urbanization, which worsens environmental quality by releasing emissions of CO2 emissions into the atmosphere (Shahbaz et al., 2018). Similar outcomes were also verified by Wu et al., (2022); Shahbaz et al., (2018); Akadiri et al., (2022). The variable expenditure decentralization is also a significant contributing factor to CO2 emissions in OECD countries. The coefficient value of FDEC indicates that as it increases by one unit, the CO2 emissions increase by 4.3294 units. In contrast, the variable revenue fiscal decentralization negatively and significantly related to the CO2 emissions. The coefficient value of -8.5846 indicates that as it increases by one unit the CO2 emissions lead to decline by 4.3294 units. It suggests that revenue fiscal decentralization is essential for improving institutional quality, using fiscal spending

better, and internalizing the negative effects of environmental degradation (Hinton et al., 2018; Udeagha & Breitenbach, 2023). It suggests FDEC increases investment, but it also increases the risk that local governments won't invest enough in environmental protection, which would increase CO₂ emissions (Oates, 1999; Hinton et al., 2018). These outcomes were also confirmed by Ji et al., (2021); Xiao-Sheng et al., (2022).

Now, considering the control variables of the study, it is found that energy use is directly and significantly related to CO₂ emissions. The coefficient EU indicates that as it increases by one unit the CO₂ emissions lead to an increase by 0.0014 units. It implies that more energy use enhances atmospheric pollutant levels and leads to environmental degradation. These results were also supported by Rehman et al., (2021); Yuan et al., (2022). Similarly, total population is found to be directly and significantly related to CO₂ emissions. The coefficient POP indicates that as it increases by one unit, the CO₂ emissions increase by 0.0334 units. It indicates that rapid population growth threatens the environment through accelerating industrialization and urbanization, intensifying agriculture, and destroying natural areas (Ray & Ray, 2011). Lastly, the variable inflation rate is found to be negatively and significantly related to the CO₂ emissions. The coefficient INF indicates that as it increases by one unit, the CO₂ emissions decline by -0.2108 units. It suggests that inflation instability enhances environmental performance, suggesting that greater price volatility reduces uncertainty and deters investment and consumption, which in turn enhances environmental quality (Ahmad et al., 2021).

Table 4: Lon-Run ARDL Estimates

Dependent Variable: CO₂ Emissions				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
SGI	0.2761	0.0921	2.9973	0.0031
PGI	0.6561	0.1301	5.0402	0.0000
EGI	0.3266	0.0460	7.0901	0.0000
FDEC	4.3294	2.0064	2.1577	0.0322
FDRC	-8.5846	1.6962	-5.0608	0.0000
EU	0.0014	0.0001	9.5287	0.0000
POP	0.0334	0.0053	6.2792	0.0000
INF	-0.2108	0.0260	-8.1105	0.0000

Source: Author's Calculations

The panel ARDL model also provides short-run error correction form. The outcomes of short-run ECM are displayed in Table 5. The outcomes imply that the coefficient of ECM(-1) turns out to be negative and statistically significant. It suggests that at 12.35 percent, errors become corrected while moving towards long-run equilibrium in case of disturbances.

Table 5: Panel ARDL Short Estimates

Dependent Variable: CO₂ Emissions				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
ECM(-1)	-0.1235	0.0467	-2.6453	0.0088
D(SGI)	-0.0056	0.1247	-0.0449	0.9642
D(PGI)	0.0264	0.1114	0.2371	0.8128

D(EGI)	0.0363	0.0531	0.6828	0.4956
D(FDEC)	-4.8934	4.8196	-1.0153	0.3112
D(FDRC)	-6.4770	11.0822	-0.5844	0.5596
D(EU)	-0.0028	0.0030	-0.9640	0.3363
D(POP)	12.7470	7.4070	1.7209	0.0869
D(INF)	0.0680	0.0912	0.7455	0.4569

Source: Author's Calculations

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

This study aims to investigate how fiscal decentralization and globalization affect environmental degradation in OECD countries. For this purpose, we have utilized a panel dataset of selected OECD countries based on data availability from 1995 to 2020. For data analysis, panel ADF test and panel ARDL model are applied to the data. The study showed that globalization and fiscal decentralization is significantly related to the environmental deterioration in OECD countries. Globalization, marked by increased levels of international trade, financial flows, and technologies, has contradictory environmental effects in OECD countries. Similarly, expenditure decentralization is a contributing factor to environmental degradation in OECD countries. In contrast, revenue decentralization is negatively and significantly related to environmental degradation in OECD countries. The control variables of the study population and energy use are also contributing factors to environmental degradation in OECD countries. In contrast, the inflation rate is reducing environmental degradation in OECD countries. The outcomes imply that fiscal decentralization and globalization increase the environmental degradation in OECD countries. Therefore, these countries must implement policies that curtail the adverse effects of globalization and fiscal decentralization on the environment.

The study also has important policy implications. First, OECD countries need to collaborate with other countries for policymaking to tackle global environmental. Secondly, OECD countries should restructure and improve their taxation procedures to reflect the economic and political climates in which they live, ensuring institutional support for the growth of the green economy. Thirdly, with the help of local governments, the central government should ensure that environment policies and laws in the country should be well utilized to minimize carbon emissions and other forms of environmental contamination. Lastly, OECD countries should promote globalization by encouraging foreign organizations to invest in green energy projects and facilitate green technology in a country.

6. References

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